

Empowering Leadership, Informal Workplace Learning, Principal Instructional Management and Transformative Leadership: A Structural Equation Model on Personal Professional Development Efforts among Public School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the significance of the influence of empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, and transformative leadership to the personal professional development of the public secondary school teachers in Region XI. Further, it endeavored to determine the best fit model representing the causal relationships of the variables using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to the 410 public secondary school teachers in Region XI, Philippines who were determined through stratified random sampling. Findings revealed very high levels of empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, transformative leadership; and high level of personal professional development. Subsequently, there is a significant correlation between empowering leadership and personal professional development; informal workplace learning personal professional development; principal instructional management personal professional development; and transformative leadership personal professional development. Further, the results showed that the best fit model was model 3 showing the direct causal relationships of empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, and transformative leadership on the personal professional development. The variables are now defined in terms of the retained indicators namely personal professional development in terms of education and cultural development, and keep up to date with related media and publications; empowering leadership with coaching and showing concern/interacting with team; informal workplace learning with reflection and intent to learn; principal instructional management with frame the school goals and provide incentives for learning; and transformative leadership with affective employee commitment and transformational leadership. Findings are indicative on the policy review on the framework for professional development that would support the needs of the teachers.

Keywords: empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, and transformative leadership on the personal professional development, structural equation modeling, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The limited access of teachers to quality professional development and the episodic versus sustained and intensive training development have raised problems in carrying out teacher related performances. Asiyah et al. (2021) stated that the quality of education is largely determined by the quality of teachers, which further depends upon their continuous professional development. On this note, Osman and Warner (2020) revealed in their findings that a number of teachers gave less attention to their personal professional development, hence, the noted missing link in the actual practice of their profession. Meanwhile, Sims and Fletcher-Wood (2021) identified that one stop workshop, variety of applications and comprehensions, topic specialization and applicability to workplace are some of the common problems facing the effective professional development practices.

Enhancing and preserving teacher quality is contingent upon professional development, which has a knock-on impact in the classroom (Fairman et al., 2022). Emphasis is placed on the efforts that teachers personally expended to access high-quality professional development opportunities because this can bring about significant improvements in their competencies and capabilities (Bowman et al., 2022). Moreover, teachers are expected to undergo continual professional development programs (PDPs) to keep themselves abreast with the changing pedagogical methods, technology, and students' needs (Li & Zhang, 2023).

On the other hand, there are certain factors that may influence the teachers' personal professional development efforts. A number of literatures supported the link between empowering leadership and personal professional development efforts of the teachers. Accordingly, empowering leadership influences the teachers' level of expending efforts towards access, and involvement in professional development (Zamin&Hussin, 2021). Similarly,

van Assen (2020) asserted that the felt empowerment of teachers is correlated with their inclination to undertake steps to achieve their targets for professional development.

Concurrently, the social and practice-oriented nature of informal workplace learning where learning emerged as reciprocal and active process posed a significant influence of the personal professional development efforts of the teachers (Holmgren & Sjöberg, 2022). Teachers showed benefits from informal workplace learning specifically on the extent of knowledge sharing that took place in the workplace (Bada et al., 2020). In the same stance, Colognesi et al. (2020) posited that informal workplace learning such as exchange of feedback and casual information sharing with colleagues create a conducive environment for professional development. Further, their findings underscored the improvement of the teachers' personal drive to undertake relevant trainings for professional development.

Subsequently, principal instructional management has been linked to the teachers' persistent involvement in personal professional development with the aim of achieving the common goals of the academe (Tang et al., 2023). The claim is substantiated in the findings of Bayawa and Guhao (2022) showing the significant correlation between the school principal's extent of instructional management to the level of the teachers' personal professional development efforts. Moreover, Kilag and Sasan (2023) claimed in their findings that the school principal's instructional leadership as evident in their ways of providing constructive feedback and promoting learning opportunities were substantial in motivating the teachers to pursue personal professional development.

Further, transformative leadership significantly affect the teachers' efforts for personal professional development by leading them to set their personal expectations for their personal professional growth (Lin et al., 2022). In support, Bellibaş et al. (2021), found that transformative leadership is a significant precursor to the teachers' personal professional development efforts. With this, school principals who made use of transformative leadership approaches can significantly impact the teachers' endeavors to work for their professional development. Similarly, Harsono et al. (2023) pointed out that the school principal's transformative leadership positively influences the teachers' self-efficacy where personal professional development efforts can be gauged.

With due considerations of the aforementioned relationships, the researcher is guided with the Conceptual Model illustrated in Figure 1 which serves as the hypothetical model that reflects the direct causal relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables. As shown, the exogenous variables of this study are empowering leadership of school heads, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, and transformative leadership. On the other hand, the endogenous variable is personal professional development. Latent variables are not immediately observed and cannot be measured directly.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Empowering Leadership of School Heads, Informal Workplace Learning, Principal Instructional Management and Transformative Leadership A Structural Equation Model on Personal Professional Development among Public School Teachers

Empowering leadership is framed from the work of Arnold, et al (2000) with the following indicators: coaching; participative decision-making; leading by example; informing; and showing concern/interacting with the team. Improving school administration will provide a realistic framework for the overall development of teaching staff. Organizational leaders in schools must be aware of how to execute suitable changes that are acceptable if they are to survive and improve by workers (Beycioglu&Kondakci, 2021).

The empowering leadership style is thought to contribute to the tendency of workers to change. Accordingly, empowering leadership is anchored to the concept that supervisors trust their employees' abilities, emphasize the value of their work, include their employees in decision-making, and minimize or remove bureaucratic restrictions on their employees (Allison, 2021). Mere encouragement to the teachers is insufficient for them to grow professionally. O'Donoghue and Van Der Werff (2022) argued that effective empowerment leadership is critical for the teachers to be self-sufficient to decide for their professional growth.

Mohamadi and Ghanbari (2022) emphasized balancing as the importance of teachers' organizational learning and professional development and examined how school administrators' empowering and visionary leadership influences teachers' tendencies to change. Akkaya (2023) posited that empowering leadership behavior of school principals have a significant impact on the degrees of self-efficacy in the teachers decision to pursue personal growth among teachers. Further, Celik and Konan (2021) argued that empowering leadership of school heads predict the teachers' efficacy to undertake personal efforts for their professional development.

A conceptual framework of indicators in informal workplace learning includes antecedents, processes, and learning outcomes to blue-collar workers following an input-process-output perspective initiated by Pavlou (2021). The findings establish a basis for future longitudinal studies and theory building in workplace learning research, and they provide managers in organizations with guidance to promote IWL. Studies noted that informal workplace learning can initiate proactive motivation among teachers (Decius et al., 2021; Huang & Lai, 2020).

Huang and Wang (2021) expressed in their findings that informal workplace learning is a significant driver of the teachers' personal professional development efforts. Other than that, the authors also underscored that school atmosphere has a variable impact on the informal workplace learning activities of different teachers. In addition, Kittel and Seufert (2023) highlighted the strong correlation between informal learning and the employees personal professional development. Employees depend on metacognitive methods, such as monitoring and regulation, to facilitate their informal learning.

In terms of the school principal's instructional management, the effectiveness of the strategies and action plans are measured through the educational outcomes (Ikram et al., 2021). School principals are one of the important links to academic achievement (Honig & Rainey, 2019). A highly effective instructional management can influence the educational outcomes positively; thereby increasing the achievement by up to 10 percentile points on standardized tests in a year (Ridwan, 2021).

Concurrently, effective instructional management entails sufficient resource allocation (Hallinger et al., 2020). In this era of budget constraints, principals have limited options for providing financial incentives to their instructors. Furthermore, one investigation that assessed the relative effects of money, acclaim, and public recognition discovered that money was only marginally more effective than praise as an incentive. It is evident that money is less cost-effective. This implies that the principal should optimize the utilization of both formal and informal methods to offer instructors recognition when it is warranted (Hoque et al., 2021).

According to Azainil (2021), a school's leadership plays a significant role in how well instructors do their tasks and how successfully schools accomplish their objectives. Due to effective planning and learning management, the principal's instructional leadership influences the caliber of competence and teacher performance. The utilization of instructional practices that raise students' achievement and teachers' openness to adopt new concepts are strongly correlated with teacher self-efficacy (Philipp, 2022). The efficacy and accomplishments of the students are also impacted by the professionalism and work satisfaction of the teachers (Tang et al., 2023). Principals' instructional leadership positively impact the teachers' personal professional development efforts (Suyudi et al., 2022).

The latent transformative leadership conceptualizes its impact to the teachers' innate desire to grow professionally (Kang, 2021). Transformative school leaders assume the role of overseeing all stakeholders all units and be able to convert a potential transformation of the school into a realistic one (Wijaya et al., 2022). Interestingly, the transformative leadership of the school principal is capable of fostering commitment and cooperation in the development, enhancement, and transformation of the learning quality, as well as the management of educational quality administration (Malla et al., 2020).

To enhance the school's positive reputation and become the community's preferred choice for sending their children to school, educational institutions must implement a transformative leadership style through the principal's role as a manager (Halim & Rofiki, 2022). Transformative leadership style enables school principals to focus on positive changes and growth of the human resource and the institution in general. Hence, school principals demonstrating transformative leadership have clear directions and can lead the school towards realizing them (Zhang & Koshmanova, 2021).

The study is mainly anchored to the Professional Development Model, a theory of change used to guide intervention program development and evaluation as articulated by Rossi et al. (2004). This model is a framework where relevant inputs are employed to support judicious intervention choices for professional development. In support to this is Bandura's Social Learning Theory which posited that the individual's intention to acquire knowledge and develop skills occurs through observations and social interaction. As argued in Garner and Kaplan (2023), teachers used the information from the observed behaviors of others such as their colleagues and school heads to generate new behavior. The presence of a model is crucial in their efforts for professional development.

In support, teachers' professional mindfulness plays a crucial role in implementing changes in daily teaching practices. This involves the teachers' ability to regulate themselves and utilize metacognitive activities, self-observation, self-judgment, and self-reflection (Linde et al., 2023). Moreover, Guilbaud et al. (2021) emphasized that avenues for professional growth should have an increased accessibility. Teachers had a positive perception on personal professional growth provided that they have the necessary resources.

The latent variables in this study are specifically anchored to supporting theories. Empowering leadership theory is anchored on the theory of psychological empowerment popularized by Perkins and Zimmerman (1995) use to understanding how individuals can be empowered in various contexts, including work, education, and community settings. It has two models namely motivational model and exchanged-based models. Motivational models used for explaining the association of subordinates' work outcomes and holds the idea that empowered employees can feel being rewarded with something intrinsic for their contributions to their work duties (Conger & Kanungo, 1988; Thomas & Velthouse, 1990) and have a higher level of

psychological empowerment (Spreitzer, 1995) through supervisor's empowering leadership behavior. This higher level of psychological empowerment then motivates employees to be loyal to perform at a higher level. The exchange-based model holds that empowering leadership behaviour can enhance subordinates' feeling of being respected, cared for and recognized by the supervisor and hence can cultivate a higher level of trust in the organization (Hutchison et al., 1986).

Subsequently, a theory of learning developed by Kolb (1984) will be of great emphasis in this study. Informal Workplace learning has captivated significant attention in recent years. This has made enticing interest among researchers. Thus, it is possible that the concept of informal learning is connected with the theory of learning. in this study. Kolb's (1984) learning cycle theory which distinguish formal and informal learning. Informal learning according to this theory is not typically classroom-based or highly structured nor institutionally sponsored. This theory is supported by a study of Marsick and Watkins's (1997) which emphasized that informal learning can either be planned and unplanned and structured or unstructured. This idea is also supported in the study of Berg and Chyung (2008) wherein they viewed informal learning occurred in outside work setting.

Additionally, the study will make use of the Instructional Leadership Model idea made popular by Hallinger and Murphy (as cited in Hallinger 2010), Murphy's Instructional Leadership Framework and Weber's Instructional Leadership Model (1996). The definition of instructional leadership, according to Hallinger (2010), is "a strong, directive leadership that directly addresses curriculum and instructional practices." They thought that the institution's effectiveness, particularly in terms of teaching and learning, is a result of its instructional leaders. The model, which consists of three basic aspects, is extensively utilized because of its high validity and reliability. (defining mission, managing instructional programs, and promoting positive culture). Murphy emphasized the prime framework elements are as follows: developing the mission and goal, promoting quality instruction and monitoring student progress, promoting an inclusive environment of learning, and creating a supportive working environment. While Weber's Instructional Leadership Model (1996) supported five essential domains of instructional leadership which include: defining the mission, managing the curriculum and instruction, promoting a positive learning environment, observing and improving instruction, and assessing the instructional program.

Finally, the transformative leadership theory of Shields (2016) emphasized that educational institutions may promote democratic society by addressing topics such as democracy, civic life, and citizenship, which in turn leads to the engagement of well-informed and compassionate individuals. This is also anchored to the social exchange theory of Homans (1958) which posited that a relationship between two individuals is formed by evaluating the costs and benefits involved. Alazeezi and Zainol (2022) argued that social exchange theory highlights the importance of interdependence in social interactions. To be more explicit, this particular mode of interaction between leaders of public entities and their employees fosters a greater level of engagement from the employees in their organizational responsibilities, leading them to offer more to the organization's service beyond what is often required of them in their official positions. Recent literature showed that transformative leadership creates positive environments that inspire and motivate the individual employees; thereby making them feel valued in the organization (Cabayag&Guhao, 2024; Espita&Guhao, 2022).

Studies on teachers' professional development focused mainly on making professional development programs relevant (Fairman et al., 2021; Sancar et al., 2021), designing effective programs (YurtsevenAvci et al., 2020), and even on factors that motivate or impede teachers from attending development programs (Popova et al., 2022). The context of the aforementioned studies focus on how professional development is framed and on how teachers respond on them. However, whether public school teachers in the Department of Education expend efforts to pursue personal professional development, and the best fit model showing the significant factors that may augment the process remain unclear. With these, the researcher deems it imperative to conduct a study using SEM to ascertain the factors that significantly influence the teachers' personal professional development efforts.

The conduct of the study is crucial in maintaining the quality of the educational outcomes. Svendsen (2020) asserted that the failure of teachers to expend considerable efforts for their personal professional development would result to stagnant instructional practices. This may further result to poor engagement with the students which negatively impact the educational outcomes.

The study posed a significant impact on the global scale considering the fact that quality of teachers influences the human resource of the globe. Teachers who invest more in their professional development are more likely to be effective, ensuring global education quality. Subsequently, teachers who made use of updated, innovative strategies as a result of their professional development efforts are most likely able to produce students who are productive and innovative. The students may directly benefit from the personal professional development efforts of their teachers as direct recipients of the instructional innovations and practices. Future researchers who wish to conduct exploration studies and or explore additional factors influencing personal professional development efforts of the teachers may utilize the findings of this study.

METHOD

This section discusses the research respondents, materials and instruments, design, and methodology.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 410 public secondary school teachers in Region XI. The sample size was determined through Raosoftonline calculator from a total population of 17,647 public secondary school teachers in Region XI. The estimated sample size was calculated based on a response rate of 50%, a confidence interval of 96%, and a margin of error of 5%. Raosoft online calculator has been recognized in several researches as a valid way of determining the sample size (Al-Balas et al., 2020; Saleh Faidah et al., 2019). The respondents were appropriate since the researcher

would like to find out in a broader scope whether there is a relationship among (EL) Empowering Leadership of School Heads, (IWL) Informal Workplace Learning, (IL) Principal's Instructional Leadership and (TL) Transformative Leadership of School Heads and their respective influence on the professional development of the public secondary school teachers in a regional scale.

This survey included samples from each of the 11 school's division in Davao Region. The sampling was identified through stratified random sampling. This technique, according to Creswell (2015), establishes the sampling size by dividing the population into smaller units known as strata where a sufficient number of respondents per division were identified. With this, the number of respondents per division were as follows: Panabo City, 17 (5%), Davao City 108 (27%); Tagum City 23 (6%); Davao del Norte 41 (10%); Davao de Oro, 69 (17%); Davao del Sur 34 (9%); Digos City, 15 (4%); Mati City 14 (4%); Davao Oriental 37 (10%); Island Garden City of Samal 12 (3%); and Davao Occidental, 29 (5%).

All secondary school teachers in DepEd Region XI had the chance to be chosen as respondent for this study. However, teachers from the private secondary schools, and public and private elementary schools were excluded in the study group. True to the voluntary nature of their participation, they were informed of their right to withdraw anytime should they find any of the part of their participation as uncomfortable for them to continue. This research prioritized the secondary teachers as respondents since secondary teachers require consistent upgrading through professional development since they have specific subject specialization. Content and skills upgrading were necessary for them to abreast with the current trends relevant to their area of specialization.

The present endeavor was conducted in the southernmost region of Mindanao. Region XI is comprised of five provinces, namely Davao de Oro, Davao del Norte, Davao del Sur, and Davao Occidental. The Davao Gulf is encompassed by the surrounding region, with Davao City serving as its central point within the region. The region in question has been inhabited by a variety of ethnic groups, among them the Boholanos, Cebuanos, and Ilonggos, which are considered to be the primary tribes. The Maranaos, Manobos, Maguindanaos, T'bolis, Bagobos, B'laans, Samals, Mansaka, and Agtas are among the various ethnic groups present in the region.

Based on the readings regarding personal professional development, the researcher noticed that there were no existing studies in Region XI that demonstrated the causal relationship among the variables being focused in this study. Specifically, between empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management and transformative leadership and how these may influence the professional development efforts of the public secondary school teachers. Additionally, the researcher is currently a school head in public secondary school in Region XI; thereby establishing the personal stake of the researcher on this point of inquiry. There is also no precise data or figure that depicts the personal professional development efforts of the public secondary school teachers in Region XI as a support of the MATATAG Agenda of the Department of Education.

Materials and Instrument

To capture the needed data, the researcher utilized adapted questionnaires. There were five sets of instruments that were utilized in this study. The instrument for empowering leadership was adapted from the Arnold, et al (2000). This tool has contains 38 statements that measures specific indicators. Meanwhile, the instrument for informal workplace learning was adapted from the work of Decius, et al (2019). This tool has 24 statements where there were six statements for each of the following indicators: experience/action; feedback; reflection; and intent to learn. The third instrument was adapted from the principal instructional management rating scale (PIMRS) of O'Donnell and White (as cited in Pettigrew, 2013) with 50 statements to measure the instructional management of the school principals. Transformative leadership scale was adapted from the research instrument utilized in the work of Alazeezi and Zainol (2022) which consisted of 22 statements. Finally, personal professional development efforts were measured using the instrument adapted from the work of Balbag, et al (2017) with 29 statements.

The instruments were rated based on the respondents' level of agreement and disagreement which ranged from strong agreement to strong disagreement. The rating scale used in this study assigned a value of five (5) to Strongly Agree (SA), indicating that the statement is consistently observed. A value of four (4) was assigned to Agree (A) indicating that the statement is often observed. Three (3) was for Neither Agree nor Disagree (NA), indicating that the statement is observed occasionally. Disagree (D) was assigned with a value of two (2), indicating that the statement is rarely observed. Finally, Strongly Disagree (SD) was assigned with a value of one (1), indicating that the statement is not observed.

The final version of the instruments was in place after thorough content validation and analysis of their internal consistency before these were administered. The instrument for Empowering Leadership has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.942 implying excellent reliability level. Meanwhile, Informal Workplace Learning scale has an internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) equivalent to 0.983 which means that this instrument has an excellent reliability level. The instrument for Principal Instructional Management has a Cronbach's alpha equivalent to 0.985 implying excellent reliability level. Reliability of the instrument Transformative Leadership has a Cronbach's alpha 0.982 which attested for its excellent reliability level. Lastly, Personal Professional Development efforts instrument has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.980 which means that the instrument has excellent reliability.

Design and Procedure

In this study, the researcher used a quantitative non-experimental research design, specifically, a structural Equation Model (SEM) to create the best-fit model. Quantitative-non-experimental research design pertains to research studies that lack the random assignment of participants to various conditions or treatments; relationship between variables were observed without actively altering or controlling them (Gopalan et al., 2020). The emphasis lies in elucidating and scrutinizing the correlation between variables rather than establishing causation (Mohajan, 2020).

The structural equation model accommodates both continuous variables and categorical variables such as ordered and dichotomous indicators. This method offers large-sample chi-square fit tests and standard errors of estimates for scenarios that have not been previously addressed (Taherdoost,

2022). This approach was appropriate since this incorporated both empirical statements, which were descriptive statements about the actual meaning of instances rather than normative claims about what the cases should be, as well as processes. Additionally, it employed empirical analyses designed to ascertain the extent to which a norm or standard was met. Ultimately, the numerical data collected was subjected to rigorous analysis using mathematical procedures.

Logical steps were undertaken by the researcher in gathering the data for this study. First, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the office of the Regional Director to conduct this study to the following schools in the region. With the approval of the Regional Director, the researcher sought the permission of the school's division superintendents to distribute the validated survey questionnaires to the respondents of the study. Second, when the school's division superintendents approved the letter, the researcher sought permission to the school principal to conduct the study, the researcher arranged the schedule of the distribution of the questionnaires to the respondents with the principal. The researcher gave the instruction to the respondents, translated the question into vernacular if necessary and entertained questions for them to fully understand the survey. The retrieval of the questionnaires were done at least 2 weeks after the distribution. The data were tallied and presented to the statistician for statistical treatment. The collection of data started in the last week of January, 2024 and were completed in the last week of March, 2024.

The assessment and interpretation of the levels of empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, transformative leadership, and personal professional development efforts, was done by extracting the mean. After that, Pearson r was used to establish whether there were meaningful connections between the variables. Finally, a system of variables' influenced patterns was examined using path analysis. In evaluating the goodness of fit of the models, the following indices were computed and should meet the criteria: CMIN/DF should be <2 with a p -value >0.05 (Tabachnick&Fidell, 2007), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) should be >0.95 , Comparative Fit Index (CFI) should be >0.95 , Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) should be >0.95 , Normative Fit Index (NFI) should be >0.95 and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) should be <0.05 and P of close Fit (PCLOSE) of >0.05 .

Additionally, the researcher adhered to the ethical standards throughout the study by following the procedural assessments and standard criteria established by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Center (UMERC). Furthermore, in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher ensured that the respondents' private information was kept private.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following part offers a complete summary of the results attained from the data-collecting method. The results are presented in alignment with the planned objectives that were set for this study. Furthermore, the research encompasses exposing the final determination of the null hypothesis. Moreover, this study assimilates and general investigation of the pertinent academic works to offer validation and authentication for its findings.

Empowering Leadership

Presented in Table 1 is the overall mean level of Empowering Leadership is 4.32, indicating a very high level. The standard deviation (SD) for this measure is 0.49. The indicator "Leading by Example" has the highest mean rating of 4.42, described as very high. On the other hand, the indicator "Participative Decision Making" has the lowest rating which is 4.19; described as high.

Table 1

Level of Empowering Leadership

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Leading by Example	0.52	4.42	Very High
Participative Decision-Making	0.59	4.19	High
Coaching	0.51	4.32	Very High
Informing	0.56	4.41	Very High
Showing Concern/Interacting with the Team	0.62	4.26	Very High
Overall	0.49	4.32	Very High

This suggests that the leader exhibits strong empowering leadership behaviors across various dimensions, including leading by example, participative decision-making, coaching, informing, and showing concern/interacting with the team. The very high level of empowerment and engagement within the team reflects positively on the leader's effectiveness in motivating, developing, and empowering their team members.

The finding is indicative that when employees feel supported by their supervisors, they become more motivated. Being consistently informed on the processes of the organization gives them the feeling of empowerment. Zamin and Hussin (2021) pointed out that teachers looked at their supervisors

as someone who influences them; leading them by example. Moreover, it is in cognizance with Allison (2021) who posited that employees felt empowered by leaders who provided opportunities for them to improve through coaching and fair interaction.

Informal Workplace Learning

Table 2 presents the level of Informal Workplace Learning. The overall mean for this variable is 4.23, described as very high, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.54. “*Intent to Learn*” has a mean rating of 4.34, described as very high; the highest rated indicator. Contrary to this, the indicator “*Feedback*” showed the lowest rating with a mean of 4.12, described as high.

Table 2

Level of Informal Workplace Learning

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Experience/Action	0.52	4.19	High
Feedback	0.66	4.12	High
Reflection	0.61	4.29	Very High
Intent to Learn	0.66	4.34	Very High
Overall	0.54	4.23	Very High

The finding shows that the teachers have a very high regard in their intention to learn as evident in their perceived level of learning something new at work and with their colleagues. This implies that they are very highly engaged in learning through their daily interactions. This also includes experiences and informal discussions with their colleagues. Meanwhile in terms of reflection, the finding shows that they put very high considerations on reflecting about the quality of their work and how they can make positive improvements. The demonstration of very high reflection on the work that they do implies that the teachers are more adaptable to the changes in the educational framework, programs, and innovations. The informal exchange and knowledge within the workplace made them incorporate new instructional strategies that supports quality outcomes in the academe.

The findings parallel to the notion of Holmgren and Sjoberg (2022) that the teachers’ engagement in professional discussions with their colleagues and adapting innovations in school is a reciprocal and active process. Tang et al. (2023) emphasized that the teachers’ decision to improve their craft emanate from their daily interaction with their colleagues, their supervisors and their immersion with the educational practices. Further, the finding is in cognizance with Kolb’s learning cycle theory (1984) emphasizing that informal learning is not a structured learning, however, this is a crucial support mechanism in enabling the teachers to adapt effective methodologies.

Principal Instructional Management

Presented in Table 3 is the level of Principal Instructional Management which shows that overall, it has a rating of 4.31 with a descriptive equivalent of very high and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.54.

Table 3

Level of Principal Instructional Management

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Frame the School Goals	0.547	4.40	Very High
Communicate the School Goals	0.568	4.43	Very High
Supervise and Evaluate Instruction	0.656	4.30	Very High
Coordinate the Curriculum	0.661	4.31	Very High
Monitor Student Progress	0.663	4.25	Very High
Protect Instructional Time	0.634	4.26	Very High
Maintain High Visibility	0.693	4.13	High
Provide Incentives for Teachers	0.614	4.32	Very High
Promote Professional Development	0.606	4.36	Very High
Provide Incentives for Learning	0.591	4.36	Very High

Overall	0.543	4.31	Very High
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The very high level of this variable is mostly ascribed by the indicator with the highest mean rating – “*Communicate the School Goals.*” This has a mean of 4.43, described as very high. Conversely, the indicator “*Maintain High Visibility.*” showed the lowest rating of 4.13 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This table suggests that teachers considered their school heads as effective managers of various aspects of instruction within the school, including setting goals, communication, supervision, curriculum coordination, monitoring student progress, protecting instructional time, providing incentives for teachers and learning, and promoting professional development. This result is consistent with the investigation by Bada et al. (2020), who found out that school principal gave communicating school mission the highest ranking. This indicates that teachers think the principal did a great job explaining the school's objective to them. Therefore, a key educational element that would improve student accomplishment and school effectiveness is the principals' instructional leadership. Similar to this, teachers' instruction may be impacted by the principal's capacity to establish an environment that is instructionally focused. There, unambiguous school objectives are articulated. Principals have the ability to significantly impact teachers' professional growth through targeted instructional leadership techniques, which can then have an impact on student achievement outcomes. While another result of the study presented by Ghavifekr et al. (2019) revealed a more compelling top instructional leadership function is related to defining the school's mission. This means a fostering a culture of open communication and collaboration, the principal can work towards bridging the perception gap and ensuring that teachers feel adequately informed and engaged in the school's goals. It is also supported in the findings of Bayawa and Guhao (2022) with the emphasis on the significant relationship between principal instructional management, school climate, teachers' personality, and teachers' self-efficacy. There is a partial mediation on the effect of school climate and teachers' personality on the relationship between principal instructional management and self-efficacy among elementary teachers.

Transformative Leadership

Presented in Table 4 is the level of Transformative Leadership showing an overall mean of 4.24 with a descriptive equivalent of very high and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.57. Consequently, the very high level of the variable Transformative leadership is due to the very high level of the majority of the indicators. Specifically, “*Transformational Leadership*” is rated the highest with a mean rating of 4.30, described as very high. On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest rating is “*Organizational Citizenship*” with a mean of 4.18, described as high.

Table 4

Level of Transformative Leadership

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Affective Employee	0.65	4.24	Very High
Job Satisfaction	0.68	4.24	Very High
Organizational Citizenship	0.61	4.18	High
Transformational Leadership	0.59	4.30	Very High
Overall	0.573	4.24	Very High

The very high level of transformative leadership as attributed by the indicator affective employee is a manifestation of the teachers' very strong sense of belongingness to their work, as well as their personal attachment. The finding also showed that the teachers are highly satisfied with

their job specifically attributed by their capacity to adapt changes and recognize the mechanisms that are helpful in the performance of their functions. Moreover, the very high level of transformational leadership is a manifestation of how the teachers feel that they can achieve their goals. Importantly, this manifested their capacity to develop the strengths of others. This result coincides with the study of (Espita&Guhao, 2022) which pertains to the intention of building trust, wholesome relationships, and a commitment to the values defended by the officials of a school. It is in line with earlier studies showing that the Transformational leadership is associated with creating favorable surroundings in which people work as inspiring and motivating, providing intellectual stimulation, and fostering individualized consideration. It is also consistent to the result study of Cabayag&Guhao (2024) that implies a perceived evaluations and remarks in their school leaders that can be used to deduce the perception of transformational leadership, which supports a feeling of value within the organizational setting to further a clear and genuine sincere and committed transformation of leadership among its constituents.

Personal Professional Development Efforts

Presented in Table 5 is the level of Personal Professional Development Efforts which shows that overall, that the level of the respondents' personal professional development is 4.15, with a descriptive equivalent of high and a standard deviation of 0.53. Most of the indicators attributed to the high level of the variable. Importantly, the indicator “*Keep up to Date with Related Media and Publications*” has a mean of 4.20 and a descriptive equivalent of very high. Nevertheless, the indicators “*Educational and Cultural Development*” and “*Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies*” have the lowest rating with an average of 4.10, described as high.

Table 5

Level of Personal Professional Development

Indicators	SD	Mean	D.E.
Specialization	0.51	4.19	High
Educational and Cultural Development	0.62	4.10	High
Professional Communication with the Shareholders	0.60	4.15	High
Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies	0.61	4.10	High
Keep up to Date with Related Media and Publications	0.60	4.20	Very High
Overall	0.53	4.15	High

Related media in the context of personal professional development refers to various forms of content, resources, and platforms that individuals can utilize to enhance their skills, knowledge. The study's results are consistent with the findings of Linde et al. (2023) teachers must not only incorporate technology into their courses to offer top-notch learning possibilities, but they must also continue to learn in this format due to the ongoing process of digitalization. Further the research analyses teachers' self-evaluation of the impact of the online TPD course on their knowledge and skills in developing students' SRL skills, and data prove that both teachers' theoretical understanding and competence in developing students' SRL skills can be significantly improved through this format of TPD.

Moreover, an alternative way has emerged in this current time, online learning professional development training has a major impact on accessibility knowledge and practice (Guilbaud et al., 2021). Results in their studies revealed teachers requested a different kind of training is advantageous asking for one-on-one online workshops and other on-line accessibility expertise, application, and career Advancement one-on-one coaching, and flexible workshop scheduling in accordance with their schedule. Teachers possess demanding workloads and are required to incorporate new technologies into their expertise and creating educational opportunities for their learners.

Relationship between Empowering Leadership and Personal Professional Development

Table 6.1 presents the significance of the relationship between empowering leadership and personal professional development across different dimensions. In the context of this research, the significance of the relationship was tested at 0.05 level of significance. It can be garnered from the table that overall, the r-value is 0.606 with a p-value less than 0.05.

Table 6.1*Significance on the Relationship between Empowering Leadership and Personal Professional Development*

		PERSONAL PROFESIONAL DEVELOPMENT					Overall
		Specialization	Educational and Cultural Development	Professional Communication with the Shareholders	Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies	Keep up to Date with Related Media and Publications	
Leading Example	by	.484* (0.000)	.403* (0.000)	.399* (0.000)	.372* (0.000)	.429* (0.000)	.462* (0.000)
Participative Decision-Making		.461* (0.000)	.484* (0.000)	.396* (0.000)	.423* (0.000)	.495* (0.000)	.502* (0.000)
Coaching		.549* (0.000)	.512* (0.000)	.470* (0.000)	.469* (0.000)	.562* (0.000)	.569* (0.000)
Informing		.524* (0.000)	.449* (0.000)	.423* (0.000)	.402* (0.000)	.485* (0.000)	.506* (0.000)
Showing Concern/Interacting with the Team		.504* (0.000)	.501* (0.000)	.501* (0.000)	.521* (0.000)	.555* (0.000)	.575* (0.000)
Overall		.582* (0.000)	.545* (0.000)	.507* (0.000)	.508* (0.000)	.585* (0.000)	.606* (0.000)

(0.000) (0.000) (0.000) (0.000) (0.000) (0.000)

The finding implies that there is a significant relationship between the level of empowering leadership and personal professional development. When the domains of empowering leadership were analyzed singly with personal professional development, the findings show that the correlation coefficient ranges from 0.462 to 0.575 with p-values less than 0.05, denoting significant correlations.

The study's findings align with the findings of Akkaya (2023) on teachers' levels of self-efficacy in their own personal growth are impacted by the actions of school principals in the accountability sub-dimension of their empowering leadership behaviors. It is clear that principals' actions in this area will have an impact on teachers directly as well as indirectly on the school. In order to boost teachers' perceptions of their own efficacy, it is crucial that school principals display behaviors that are particularly in the supporting dimension.

Moreover, this is in cognizance of the finding of Celik and Konan (2021) which indicates that teachers' self-efficacy and organizational citizenship behaviors were favorably predicted by school principals' empowering leadership, and that teachers' self-efficacy also positively predicted their organizational citizenship behaviors. It also showed a positive correlation between teachers' organizational commitment and job performance and empowering leadership and strengthening organizational commitment through empowerment of school leadership improves teachers' work performance.

Relationship between Informal Workplace Learning and Personal Professional Development

Presented in Table 6.2 is the relationship between informal workplace learning and personal professional development. The results show that overall, there is a strong, positive, and significant relationship between informal workplace learning and personal professional development as evident in the correlational coefficient value (r-value) of 0.621 and a p-value is less than 0.05.

Table 6.2

Significance on the Relationship between Informal Workplace Learning and Personal Professional Development

Informal Workplace Learning	Personal Professional Development					Overall
	Specialization	Educational and Cultural Development	Professional Communication with the Shareholders	Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies	Keep up to Date with Related Media and Publications	
Experience/Action	.453*	.443*	.404*	.413*	.431*	.477*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Feedback	.528*	.508*	.472*	.488*	.517*	.559*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Reflection	.545*	.502*	.497*	.486*	.559*	.575*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Intern to Learn	.543*	.510*	.499*	.491*	.541*	.574*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Overall	.588*	.588*	.533*	.533*	.583*	.621*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

When analyzed individually, all of the domains of informal workplace learning pose a positive, and significant relationship with personal professional development with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.477 to 0.575.

The emerging result in Table 7 is associated with those of Huang and Wang (2021), instituting psychological capital, school climate, collaboration, and instructional creativity are all positively correlated with informal workplace learning activities among teachers. Of particular, self-reflection amplifies the benefits of most aspects of school climate. Moreover, this is in observation of the finding of Kittel and Seufert (2023) between informal learning and self-regulated learning in the workplace. Informal learning activities such as reflection or keeping up-to-date resemble self-regulated learning strategies that indicate the ability to plan, monitor, and regulate one's learning are strongly related to the metacognitive self-regulated learning strategies that resulted to strong professional improvement of workers.

Relationship between Principal Instructional Management and Personal Professional Development

Table 6.3 presents the results of the analysis on the hypothesized significance of the relationship between principal instructional management and personal professional development.

Table 6.3

Significance on the Relationship between Principal Instructional Management and Personal Professional Development

Principal Instructional Management	Personal Professional Development					Overall
	Specialization	Educational and Cultural Development	Professional Communication with the Shareholders	Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies	Keep up to Date with Related Media and Publications	
Frame the School Goals	.629* (0.000)	.502* (0.000)	.538* (0.000)	.511* (0.000)	.593* (0.000)	.615* (0.000)
Communicate the School Goals	.591* (0.000)	.445* (0.000)	.508* (0.000)	.480* (0.000)	.547* (0.000)	.570* (0.000)
Supervise and Evaluate Instruction	.653* (0.000)	.615* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.603* (0.000)	.645* (0.000)	.695* (0.000)
Coordinate the Curriculum	.655* (0.000)	.573* (0.000)	.599* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.614* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)
Monitor Student Progress	.657* (0.000)	.559* (0.000)	.589* (0.000)	.582* (0.000)	.652* (0.000)	.675* (0.000)
Protect Instructional Time	.715* (0.000)	.585* (0.000)	.602* (0.000)	.600* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)	.703* (0.000)
Maintain High Visibility	.631* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)	.574* (0.000)	.599* (0.000)	.597* (0.000)	.659* (0.000)
Provide Incentives for Teachers	.649* (0.000)	.627* (0.000)	.647* (0.000)	.599* (0.000)	.637* (0.000)	.703* (0.000)
Promote Professional Development	.687* (0.000)	.600* (0.000)	.633* (0.000)	.578* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)	.702* (0.000)
Provide Incentives For Learning	.666* (0.000)	.577* (0.000)	.592* (0.000)	.555* (0.000)	.595* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)
Overall	.751* (0.000)	.651* (0.000)	.678* (0.000)	.653* (0.000)	.715* (0.000)	.765* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The results show that overall, principal instructional management has a strong, positive and significant correlation with personal professional development with r-value of 0.765. The analysis of the individual domains of principal instructional management shows positive and significant correlations with personal professional development with correlation coefficient values ranging from 0.570 to 0.703 which were less than the set p-value of 0.05.

The findings of this study also consistent with Kilag and Sasan (2023) which revealed that instructional leadership practices were found to be correlated in promoting teacher learning and development. It emphasized the importance of leaders modeling effective teaching practices, providing feedback, and facilitating collaboration and learning opportunities and quality of teacher-administrator relationships was essential in promoting teacher professional growth. The study also revealed that teacher professional development is a continuous and ongoing process that requires sustained support from school leaders. It emphasized the need for ongoing professional development opportunities, such as workshops, mentoring, and coaching. In support, Suyudi et al. (2022) argued that the school principal's instructional leadership directly impact the teachers' desire to be professionally equipped for their learners.

Relationship between Transformative Leadership and Personal Professional Development

The statistical significance of the relationship between transformative leadership and personal professional development is shown in Table 6.4. Overall, transformative leadership posed a significant relationship with personal professional development with r-value of 0.779 and p-value of

less than 0.05. Analysis on each domain of transformative relationship to the overall personal professional development revealed correlation coefficient values ranging from 0.679 to 0.723. All of the domains of transformative leadership are positively and significantly correlated with personal professional development.

Table 6.4

Significance on the Relationship between Transformative Leadership and Personal Professional Development

Transformative Leadership	Personal Professional Development					Overall
	Specialization	Educational and Cultural Development	Professional Communication with the Shareholders	Utilization of Information and Communication Technologies	Keep up to E with Related Media and Publications	
Affective Employee	.671* (0.000)	.632* (0.000)	.643* (0.000)	.633* (0.000)	.672* (0.000)	.723* (0.000)
Job Satisfaction	.655* (0.000)	.629* (0.000)	.619* (0.000)	.600* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)	.704* (0.000)
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	.652* (0.000)	.580* (0.000)	.565* (0.000)	.623* (0.000)	.638* (0.000)	.679* (0.000)
Transformational Leadership	.715* (0.000)	.604* (0.000)	.629* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)	.715* (0.000)
Overall	.743* (0.000)	.676* (0.000)	.679* (0.000)	.681* (0.000)	.728* (0.000)	.779* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Data in table 6.4 provides insights into how specific transformative leadership practices relate to various aspects of personal professional development among employees, with statistical significance revealed R-values between 0.676 and 0.743, with p-values below 0.05.

This suggests the existence of considerable relationships. Furthermore, significant correlation was observed between each of the personal professional development efforts indicators and the overall level of transformative leadership, as indicated by r-values between 0.679 and 0.723 and p-values which are less than 0.05; thus, the present findings suggest that the correlations are indeed significant.

The findings of the current study are similar with the findings of Kang (2021) which strongly supports a positive links among transformational leadership, self-efficacy and cooperative professional development. Further the findings provided greater insight into transformational leadership and revealed mechanisms through which transformational leadership works. It clarifies the nature of the relationship between the principals' transformational leadership and CPD and facilitate a better understanding of the relationship between the principals' transformational leadership and teacher development.

Best Fit Model on Personal Professional Development Efforts

Presented in Table 7 is summary of the goodness of fit measures of the three structural equation models for the variables empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, transformative leadership, and personal professional development efforts.

Table 7

Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the

Three Structural Equation Models

Model	CMIN/DF	GFI	CFI	NFI	TLI	RMS	P-Value	P – Close
	0 < value < 2	>0.95	>0.95	>0.95	>0.95	< 0.05ea	> 0.05	> 0.05
1	5.060	.741	.891	.868	.878	.100	.000	.000
2	4.396	.888	.947	.933	.933	.091	.000	.000
3	1.450	.983	.996	.988	.993	.033	.068	.884

The tables shows that models 1 and 2 were not able to meet the criteria for a good fit model, namely: CMIN/DF $0 < \text{value} < 2$; GFI > 0.95 ; CFI > 0.95 ; NFI > 0.95 ; TLI > 0.95 ; RMSEA < 0.05 ; with P-close and p-value greater than 0.05. Significantly, it can be gleaned from the table that the structural model 3 has satisfied the criteria for a fitting model of the latent variables. This signifies that the 3rd model exhibits a parsimonious fit, which is shown in

Figure 4.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model 3 in Standardized Solution

Legend:

- coa – Coaching
- scit – Showing Concern/Interacting with Team
- EL – Empowering Leadership
- ref – Reflection
- il – Intern to Learn
- IWL – Informal Workplace Learning
- fsg – Frame the School Goals
- pil – Provide Incentives for Learning
- PIM – Principal Instructional Management
- aec – Affective Employee Commitment
- tl – Transformational Leadership
- TRANSLEAD – Transformative Leadership
- ecd – Education and Cultural Development
- kudrmp – Keep up to the date with Related Media and Publications
- PPD – Personal Professional Development

As presented in Figure 4, the goodness of fit measures of the conceptual structural equation model involving the latent variables empowering leadership, informal workplace learning, principal instructional management, transformative leadership, and personal professional development. As shown in the figure, empowering leadership to personal professional development has a β -coefficient of -0.07; informal workplace learning personal professional development has 0.16; principal instructional management personal professional development has -0.14; and transformative leadership to personal professional development has 0.97.

This implies that for unit of increase in empowering leadership, personal professional development will decrease by 0.07 standard deviations; a unit increase in the informal workplace learning will increase the personal professional development by 0.16 standard deviations; an increase per unit of principal instructional management will cause a decrease in the personal professional development by 0.14 standard deviations; while a unit increase in the transformative leadership will cause an increase in the personal professional development by 0.97 standard deviations.

A more specific description of the retained indicators in each latent variable is presented in Table 13. As shown in the table, examining singly the indicators of each variable revealed high β -coefficients or stronger effect. Empowering leadership includes coaching ($\beta=0.88$), and showing concern/interacting with team ($\beta=0.88$). For informal workplace learning, these are reflection ($\beta=0.91$), and intent to learn ($\beta=0.89$). On the other hand, principal instructional management has frame the school goals ($\beta=0.82$), and provide incentives for learning ($\beta=0.84$). Finally, transformative leadership has affective employee commitment ($\beta=0.85$), and transformational leadership ($\beta=0.85$).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions and recommendations are framed:

The felt empowering leadership is consistently observed among the public secondary school teachers. With this, school heads may provide venues where teachers feel empowered such as the implementation of teacher-led innovation programs. Teachers may be given strong autonomy and provided with resources to develop new instructional materials and strategies.

Subsequently, the informal workplace learning is also consistently observed. Hence, it is recommended that academic institutions may strengthen the collaboration between and among the administrative body, teachers and stakeholders. Regular professional learning sessions, meet and greet activities and the like, may be adapted to reinforce the quality of the informal workplace learning of the teachers.

On the other hand, principal instructional management is often observed. Therefore, it is indicative that the administrators of the educational sector may put high priority in areas that will have the greatest impact on teacher effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Moreover, the top management of the Department of Education may put on resources on creating programs that will enhance the instructional management of school principals like masterclass sessions and similar programs.

Meanwhile, transformative leadership is consistently observed. In this context the Department of Education may encourage collaboration and teamwork across diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and skill sets. Create opportunities for cross-functional collaboration, brainstorming sessions, and knowledge sharing to foster innovation and creativity. It may also cultivate a culture of continuous learning and development where mistakes are viewed as opportunities for growth and learning and encourage team members to seek out new challenges, acquire new skills, and pursue opportunities for personal and professional development. Further, regular and consistent immersion with the community and forging partnerships with the community would greatly help the teachers' felt transformative leadership.

Finally, personal professional development efforts of the public school teachers are often observed. In this precept, the Department of Education may conduct a policy review to enhance teacher commitment that encourage them to regularly reflect on their experiences, strengths, areas for growth, and lessons learned, and support them in developing a deeper understanding of themselves and their impact on others. Further, it may help in the continuous development of the teachers if data-based programs are made available similar to Teacher Pathways Project in other countries. This project closes a research gap by offering a methodical, data-rich examination of the paths that teachers chose to teach and the effects those choices and those pathways have on student accomplishment in the classroom. DepEd may venture on multi-year research which examines and pinpoints the qualities of teacher preparation programs and entry-level career trajectories that enhance student outcomes.

The third structural model is thought to be the most appropriate one because it precisely define the examined variables. The findings of this study offer suggestion against the second null hypothesis, which stated that there is no best-fit model for explaining the level of personal professional development of public-school teachers. The findings of the study substantiated Professional Development Model a theory of change used to guide intervention program development and evaluation as articulated by Rossi et al. (2004), which provides a structured approach to developing and evaluating intervention programs aimed at promoting professional development. This model is based on the Theory of Change framework, which identifies the underlying assumptions and logic behind how an intervention is expected to achieve its desired outcomes. The policy-making entity within the Department of Education may consider possibilities of policy review by which the personal professional development of teachers can be raised such as considering work load, accessibility to trainings synchronous or asynchronous, free continuing educational pursuit and institutionalize standards for teacher professional development, recognize contributions publicly and provide meaningful rewards and recognition to reinforce desired behaviors and outcomes.

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